

**THE STATUS OF HUMAN RIGHTS IN WAR ZONES: AN
APPRAISAL OF ISRAELI ATTACK ON GAZA AFTER
HAMAS'S 7 OCTOBER ATTACK**

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Abstract

On 7 October 2023, Hamas militants launched an attack against Southern Israel. More than 240 Israeli people were held captive by Hamas. In reply, the Israeli military conducted air, naval, and land assaults on Gaza, killing more than 30,000 people and displacing over 1.7 million. This recent conflict is the latest episode in the long history of Israeli-Palestine strife. The recent conflict between Israel and Palestine forced the people to turn back the pages of history to identify the root of this conflict. At the same time, it necessitates reconsidering the international legal framework for protecting human rights during armed conflict. International Humanitarian Law is a collection of rules defining the limits of action parties in armed conflicts can take. The recent Israel-Palestine armed conflict introduced new sets of violence that were unheard of to the world, as the violation of human rights in armed conflicts has become the norm and reality in modern times. The periphery of war zones is expanding daily, and it takes hold of the whole world. The West Asian region is witnessing grave violations of human rights. Mainly, occupied Palestine is one of the boiling pots in West Asia, witnessing grave violations of human rights. This paper delves into the history of the Arab-Israel conflict and identifies the causes of the recent Palestinian-Israeli armed conflict. It also sheds light on the role of Hamas in the recent armed conflict between Israel and Palestine. This paper sheds light on the international legal framework that tends to protect people's fundamental rights during armed conflicts and assesses the impact of such armed conflict on the human rights of people in these areas in light of international humanitarian law.

Keywords: Armed Conflict, Human Rights, International Humanitarian Law

1. Introduction

In 1922, the League of Nations placed Palestine under British administration in the former Ottoman territories. All these territories eventually gained independence, except Palestine. The case of Palestine was different from that of other colonies of British administration, where, in the name of administrative assistance and advice, the British incorporated the "Balfour Declaration" of 1917. The Balfour Declaration provided for the establishment of a national home for Jewish people in Palestine. This declaration resulted in a wave of Jewish migration from 1922 to 1947. The Jewish people started to settle on a large scale. The migration of Jewish people reached its peak in the year 1930 when Nazis prosecuted them. The settling of Jews in Palestine, Arabs' demands for independence from British colonialism, and their resistance against Jewish immigration led to the foundation of the rebellion of 1937. (History of the Question of Palestine, 2024).

In 1947, the United Nations prepared a plan to resolve the dispute. It proposed to split the territory of Palestine into two parts, namely, the Jewish state and the Arab state. That plan was acceptable to Jewish leaders but rejected by the Arab leaders. Due to a lack of consensus among the parties, it was never implemented. After the rejection of the 'two nations plan' by the Arabs, Israel has declared statehood. This incident intensified the conflict between Arabs and Jews. Due to the formation of Israel, thousands of Palestinians were forced to leave their motherland. That forced eviction of Palestinians from their land is called the "Al Nakba" or the "Catastrophe." Over time, the conflict between the Jews and Arabs became more intensified. Israel got control over most of the territory. Jerusalem split into two parts, namely, West Jerusalem and East Jerusalem. East Jerusalem came under the control of the Jordanian army, but West Jerusalem came under the control of the Israeli military. These areas witnessed more conflict in the following years. (Israel Gaza war: History of the conflict explained, 2024)

In the six-day war in 1967, Israel occupied the Egyptian Sinai Peninsula, Syrian Golan Heights, East Jerusalem, and the West Bank. Israel had restricted the entry of Palestinians on the pretence that it would hamper the existence of a Jewish state. (Israel Gaza war: History of the conflict explained, 2024). The foundation of HAMAS was led by Ikhwan members associated with Shaykh Yasin's al-Mujam'a al-Islami at the

Islamic University in Gaza in 1978. The HAMAS had crystalised its mission as the liberation of Palestinians and the cessation of Israeli aggression against them. (Zuhur, 2008).

In 1988, HAMAS published its charter to popularise its mission. One of the clauses in the charter expressed the killing of Jews, the destruction of Israel, and the establishment of an Islamic state in occupied Palestine as its primary objectives. Hamas has proposed a new charter in the year 2017 in which the killing of Jews has been removed as one of its objectives, but the status quo has been maintained regarding the illegal character of Israel. In the revised charter, HAMAS hinted that they may accept a future Palestinian state along the borders as it were before the six-day war. (Robinson, 2024).

After the win of elections held in 2006, HAMAS had new identities, namely, the government of Gaza and a resistance group dedicated to fighting Israel. After the election of 2006, Israel had intensified the conflict. Over the years, Israel has led various military operations, namely "Operation Cast Lead" in 2008–09, "the Pillar of Defence" in 2012, and "Protective Edge" in 2014, which resulted in the death of thousands of Palestinians. Over the years, Israel has put pressure on HAMAS in the form of an economic boycott, international isolation, repeated attacks on infrastructure, and army-led operations, and these tactics of Israeli authority have made the survival of Palestinians very miserable. (Byman, 2024, pp. 63-69).

Hamas-led attack on Israel

On the morning of 7 October 2023, HAMAS attacked Israel and covered the sky with rockets, marching towards Israel. It was like a wave of people that stormed Gaza's border. That attack by HAMAS resulted in the deaths of 1200 people, and they kept 250 as hostages. The HAMAS justified its attack as retaliation for the Israeli actions. HAMAS was content that Israeli forces had raided their holy place, "Al-Aqsa Mosque," led military operations in various parts of the territory, made thousands of Palestinian prisoners, and infringed on the modesty and respect of the women in the territory. Other reasons for that attack were to get their people who were in jail and to bring an end to the blockade of the Gaza Strip by Israel. HAMAS has fought several wars with Israel since it usurped its power in the territory, and Israel has repeatedly attacked Hamas with air strikes and sent troops into Gaza in 2008 and

2014 without a distinction between the gunmen of HAMAS and civilians. (BBC, 2024).

The role of Prisoners and their families was very significant in the 7 October attack to ensure the release of the captured. In 2006, when HAMAS captured soldier Gilad Shalit as a hostage, the Israel authority was convinced to release more than 1,000 prisoners in exchange for capture. This time, HAMAS also expected the release of thousands of prisoners against the release of hostages. But, this time, Israeli authority showed a different attitude toward its citizens and intensified the attack on Gaza, the West Bank, and Rafah. Israel also attacked the "Al Shifa Hospital" and made every possible arrangement to end the lives of civilians. The attack on Al Shifa Hospital resulted in the cessation of basic health facilities in the occupied territory. (Byman, 2024).

2. International Legal Framework Protecting Human Rights in Armed Conflict: International Humanitarian Law

In recent decades, the world has witnessed various armed conflicts that leave an unforgettable view of barbarity in their minds. The armed conflict has adversely affected the lives of millions of civilians. Serious violations of international humanitarian and human rights law stigmatised humanity. Grave violation of human rights in armed conflicts has become a common phenomenon in modern times. In certain circumstances, the breach of fundamental rights may result in genocide, war crimes, or crimes against humanity. (Commission, 2011) Humanitarian catastrophes in various parts of the world force us to resort to the law that protects humanitarian interests during armed conflicts.

I. A Historical Account

The Law of War, commonly known as the International Humanitarian Law, tends to ensure humanity and human treatment in the worst situation for human beings, namely, Armed Conflict. In ancient times, the treatment of wounded, sick, victims of war, soldiers, and prisoners of war differed according to the nature of parties, geopolitical conditions, and religious and societal beliefs. The development of international humanitarian law was gradual, and the roots of humanitarian law go very deep in history. They witnessed the universal codification of international humanitarian law in the late nineteenth century. The international community convinced itself to adopt common principles,

rules, and practices to mitigate war casualties. The bitter experiences of the past forced the international community to strike a balance between the necessity of war and the need for humanitarian consideration. (Advisory Service On International Humanitarian Law, 2004) The Treaty of Friendship between Prussia and the United States was recorded as the first step in developing the law of war. (Murphy, 2004) This treaty laid the foundation of humanitarian law. This treaty tends to protect the well-being of prisoners of war. After that, the role of the Lieber Code (A Code Prepared by Francis Lieber based on international law to protect the human rights of civilians and soldiers) was pivotal in sowing the seed for the development of the law of war. (The Laws of War: The Lieber Codes, n.d.) In 1864, as a result of the positive efforts of Henry Dunant, the Geneva Convention for the Amelioration of the Condition of the Wounded in Armies in the Field was adopted. The Geneva Convention of 1864 prepared the foundational framework for the development of international humanitarian law. (Sandoz, 1998) In 1868, the Declaration of St. Petersburg prohibiting the use of small explosives or incendiary projectiles was also an important step in this regard. (Shaw, 2008) However, these Initial steps for the development of international humanitarian law were exposed in World War II, and the shortcomings of these instruments became apparent. The Hague Convention of 1899 and 1907 are at the core of modern international humanitarian law. The Hague Law has established the law and customs of war and strictly defined the conduct of parties that must be followed during the conflict (Shaw, 2008). In the Hague Conference, a cluster of conventions was adopted on naval warfare, land warfare, and the behaviour of belligerent states to reduce casualties in war. Hague law provided a wetland for the nourishment of modern international humanitarian law. Later, the Geneva Conventions and its additional protocols were adopted and it marked the biggest achievement of humanity in the last century. (The Geneva Conventions of 1949 and their Additional Protocols, 2014) The Geneva Conventions along with its additional protocols are regarded as the Magna Carta of international humanitarian law. It contains lighting principles that tend to limit barbarous treatment and ensure humane and dignified treatment during armed conflicts. Initially, International humanitarian law was only extended to international armed conflict and thus excluded internal tensions and disturbances. However, the adoption of Protocol II paved

the way for the application of international humanitarian law to internal tensions and disturbances. (Halme-Tuomisaari, 2020)

II. International Humanitarian Law

International Humanitarian Law is the body of international law that controls the conduct of the state in the situation of armed conflict. The Geneva Conventions of 1949 form the core of the International Humanitarian Law. The four Geneva Conventions further substantiated by the additional protocol of 1977 and 2005 laid down the comprehensive framework to deal with various situations during armed conflicts. The four conventions seek to protect the different classes of people. It protects wounded, sick, shipwrecked members of the armed forces, civilians, and prisoners of war. Apart from the Geneva Conventions, there is a long list of other conventions that tend to combat the situation of human catastrophe during armed conflicts. These agreements include:

- The 1954 Convention for the Protection of Cultural Property in the Event of Armed Conflict, and its two protocols;
- The 1972 Biological Weapons Convention;
- The 1980 Conventional Weapons Convention and its five protocols;
- The 1993 Chemical Weapons Convention;
- The 1997 Ottawa Convention on anti-personnel mines;
- Optional Protocol on the Involvement of Children in Armed Conflict (What is International Humanitarian Law?, 2007)

This paper concentrated only on the four Geneva Conventions.

A. First Geneva Convention

Geneva Convention for the Amelioration of the Condition of the Wounded and Sick in Armed Forces in the Field primarily focuses on the protection of the wounded and sick, medical and religious personnel, medical units, and medical transports. The chapter I of the convention sheds light on the general principles. The Article 2 of the convention deals with the general application of the convention.

Chapter II, Chapter III, Chapter IV, and Chapter V deal with the protection of wounded and sick, medical units and establishments, certain classes of individuals, and certain categories of buildings respectively.

(Convention (I) for the Amelioration of the Condition of the Wounded and Sick in Armed Forces in the Field. Geneva, 12 August 1949)

Article 12 of the convention deals with the protection of members of the armed forces and certain other categories of persons whenever such people are sick and wounded. Article 12 ensures that such persons shall be treated humanely, respected, and protected in all circumstances. This article also ruled out the probability of distinction based on sex, race, nationality, political opinion, and religion in case of treatment when such persons fall into the hands of the other party. Article 13 extended the protection of Article 12 to the various classes of people namely members of militias or volunteer corps forming part of the armed forces, volunteer corps, Persons who accompany the armed forces without actually being members of armed forces, Members of crews including masters, pilots and apprentices of the merchant marine and the crews of civil aircraft, etc.... (Convention (I) for the Amelioration of the Condition of the Wounded and Sick in Armed Forces in the Field. Geneva, 12 August 1949)

The convention ensures the protection of wounded and sick belligerents who fall into the hands of the enemy. Article 14 declares that such persons shall be treated as prisoners of war, and the protection that is given to prisoners of war shall be extendable here. (Convention (I) for the Amelioration of the Condition of the Wounded and Sick in Armed Forces in the Field. Geneva, 12 August 1949)

Article 15 put an obligation on the parties to conflict to make every possible effort for the search and collection of the wounded and sick. The parties also make efforts to protect them against pillage and ill-treatment and ensure that they get adequate care. (Convention (I) for the Amelioration of the Condition of the Wounded and Sick in Armed Forces in the Field. Geneva, 12 August 1949)

Chapter III of the convention deals with the protection of medical establishments and hospitals. Article 19 ensures that in no circumstances the hospitals, medical units, and establishments shall not be attacked. Article 19 further provides that the medical personnel shall be allowed to perform their functions and duties freely. Article 20 extended the protection of the convention to the ships of the hospital. It ensures that the parties shall not attack the ship of the hospital from land.

(Convention (I) for the Amelioration of the Condition of the Wounded and Sick in Armed Forces in the Field. Geneva, 12 August 1949)

Chapter IV of the convention talks about the protection of certain classes of people who are not included in the abovementioned category. Article 24 sheds light on the protection of medical personnel who are imparting services for the treatment of the wounded or sick and also putting efforts into the prevention of disease. (Convention (I) for the Amelioration of the Condition of the Wounded and Sick in Armed Forces in the Field. Geneva, 12 August 1949)

This convention not only protects the person of the permanent medical personnel but also protects the personnel involved in the auxiliary services. Article 25 imparts the same protection to such persons involved in the auxiliary services as given to the permanent personnel.

Chapter v of the convention deals with the protection of buildings and materials. Article 33 ensures that if any material of the mobile medical unit falls into the hands of the enemy shall only be used for care of wounded and sick.

B. Second Geneva Convention

The Second Geneva Convention for the amelioration of the condition of the wounded, sick, and shipwrecked members of armed forces at sea aims to protect the causes of wounded, sick, and shipwrecked members of armed forces at sea.

Article 3 is a common provision in every Geneva Convention. This article lays down a very important principle that states that in a conflict of non-international character, each party is bound to apply the following provisions.

Parties shall create the distinction between the people who take part in the conflict and those who do not take part and shall treat humanely those who remain at a distance from the armed conflict.

- Parties shall treat humanely to the members of armed forces who laid down their arms.
- The Acts like violence to life and person, murder of all kinds, mutilation, cruel treatment and torture, taking of hostages, outrages upon personal dignity, humiliating and degrading treatment, and

subjection to punishment without the judgment of the lawfully constituted court shall remain prohibited with the above-mentioned peoples.

Article 4 of the convention states that whenever the conflict arises between land and naval forces of the Parties, the convention shall only be extendable to the forces on board the ship. This convention shall also protect the interest of forces deployed ashore. (Convention (II) for the Amelioration of the Condition of Wounded, Sick and Shipwrecked Members of Armed Forces at Sea. Geneva, 12 August 1949)

Article 13 of the convention lays down the list of the persons protected under the convention. The following persons get protection under the convention.

- Members of armed forces, members of militias, and volunteer corps forming part of such forces
- Members organised resistance movements
- Persons who accompany the armed forces in the capacity of civilian members of military aircraft crews, war correspondents, supply contractors, members of labour units, and any other person imparting services for the welfare of armed forces.
- Inhabitants of a non-occupied territory who, spontaneously start to resist the invading force when enemy force enters into their territory and such people had no time to form a proper armed force to resist. (Convention (II) for the Amelioration of the Condition of Wounded, Sick and Shipwrecked Members of Armed Forces at Sea. Geneva, 12 August 1949)

Article 12 deals with the protection and care of the persons mentioned in article 13. It states that such persons, who are at sea and who are wounded, sick, or shipwrecked shall be treated humanely and shall not be subjected to violence, torture, and biological experiments. Such a person shall not be left without medical assistance and not exposed to circumstances that result in contagion or infection. (Convention (II) for the Amelioration of the Condition of Wounded, Sick and Shipwrecked Members of Armed Forces at Sea. Geneva, 12 August 1949)

Further, various articles of the convention shed light on the various aspects of the protection and care of the people who are at sea. These articles majorly focus on the protection of ships, medical vehicles, the

medical establishment, and protection of any person above mentioned who falls in the hand of the enemy. (Convention (II) for the Amelioration of the Condition of Wounded, Sick and Shipwrecked Members of Armed Forces at Sea. Geneva, 12 August 1949)

C. Third Geneva Convention

Geneva Convention Relative to the Treatment of Prisoners Of War of 12 August 1949 aims to protect the interest of the prisoners of war. It is a very important and comprehensive convention that revolves around the protection of prisoners of war in every circumstance. This convention has become an instrument of great importance in the present era of war.

Article 4 of the convention requires elaborative discussion because it defines prisoners of war in respect of the present convention. According to Article 4, the following persons fall in the category of prisoners of war.

- Members of armed conflict, members of militias, and members of volunteer corps forming part of such armed forces
- Members of organised resistance groups provided that they are commanded by a person responsible for his subordinates, have a fixed distinctive sign recognisable at a distance carry arms openly and conduct their operations under the laws and customs of war
- Persons who accompany the armed forces with the authorisation of armed forces without being a member of such forces like military aircraft crews, war correspondents, supply contractors, members of labour units
- Inhabitants of a non-occupied territory who, spontaneously start to resist the invading force when the enemy force enters their territory and such people had no time to form a proper armed force to resist

Part II of the convention particularly deals with general protection to which a prisoner of war is entitled. Articles 13, 14, and 15 in Chapter II require a detailed discussion. Article 13 of the convention ensures the human treatment of the prisoners of war. It prohibits all the acts and omissions that result in death and; cause endanger to the health of prisoners. It further provides that the prisoners of war shall not be subjected to physical mutilation or to medical or scientific experiments of any kind which are not justified by the medical, dental, or hospital treatment. Article 14 of the convention particularly sheds light on the issue of respect and dignity of prisoners. It protects the person and

honour of the prisoners. It also provides special provisions for the protection of the dignity of woman prisoners.

Part III deals particularly with the aspect of captivity. Article 17 deals with the questioning of prisoners and ensures every possible protection against violence and unpleasant behaviour. It states that the prisoners shall not be subjected to physical and mental torture and coercion to extract information from the prisoners.

D. Fourth Geneva Convention

Geneva Convention Relative to the Protection of Civilian Persons in Time of War of 12 August 1949 seeks to protect the interest of civilians during the period of war or occupation. This convention is very important in the context of the recent Israel-Palestine war because the civilians are those who suffered the most in the recent armed conflict. The convention becomes operational immediately upon the outbreak of armed conflict or the start of occupation and ceases to have effect at the general close of military operations. The fourth Geneva Convention and I additional protocol of 1977 lays down the basic legal framework for the protection of the civilian population. This convention shall be applicable in cases of declared war, armed conflict between the parties, and all cases of total and partial occupation. So, under Article 2 the population residing in occupied Palestinian territory shall be entitled to protection of this convention. Article 48 of I Additional Protocol requires that the parties to the conflict have to make a distinction between the civilian population and combatants. This division between the civilian population and combatants makes the functioning of the convention smooth. After knowing about the situations that this convention covers, now, the question arises to whom this convention imparts protection. Consideration of Article 4 is required in this regard because it defines the protected person. The protected persons are those who in the case of conflict and occupation found themselves in the hands of the party of which he is not a citizen. Article 4 further provides that the person protected under I, II, and III Geneva Convention shall not be deemed a protected person for this convention. Article 13 states that the provision of part II covers whole the population of the countries in conflict without any discrimination based on nationality, caste, religion, faith, or political opinion. The convention extends special protection to the wounded and sick, as well as the infirm, and expectant mothers

through Article 16. (Convention (IV) relative to the Protection of Civilian Persons in Time of War. Geneva, 12 August 1949).

Article 14 of the convention mandates that the parties shall establish the hospitals and safety zones and localities to protect the well-being of the wounded, sick, and aged persons, children under fifteen, expectant mothers, and mothers of children under seven in its territory or occupied territory. However, Article 18 deals with the protection of these hospitals and safety zones. It states that these Civilian hospitals in no circumstances shall be attacked, shall be respected and protected by the Parties to the conflict. Article 27 lays down the provisions regarding the treatment of the protected persons. This article ensures that the protected person shall be treated humanely and protected against all acts of violence and threats. It provides provision for the protection of women against prostitution, rape, and indecent form of assault. Article 33 prohibits the imposition of collective penalties. Article 47 is an important article regarding the occupied territory. It provides the rule of inviolability of rights. This rule states that the protection given shall not be revoked by the change introduced as a consequence of a change in the government of the occupied territory or the conclusion of an agreement between the authorities of the occupied territory and the occupying power. Article 49 is relevant in respect of the recent armed conflict between Israel and Palestine because it prohibits the forcible transfer of masses. It states that masses shall not be deported forcefully from occupied territory to any territory. (Convention (IV) relative to the Protection of Civilian Persons in Time of War. Geneva, 12 August 1949)

3. Israeli Attack on Gaza Strip and International Humanitarian Law

The war zones are the areas where the rule of law is challenged and violations of human rights took place. The violation of human rights has become a normal phenomenon in armed conflicts. The recent Israel-Palestine conflict has presented new sets of violence against humanity and exposed the world to the changing contours of violence against humans. This part will assess the human rights conditions during the recent Gaza-Israel conflict in light of international humanitarian law.

1) Violation of the Right to Life

The individual's right to life and human dignity is one of a human's natural and inalienable rights. The right to life has extensive scope in modern jurisprudence. It includes the right to dignity, right to food, right to shelter, right to treatment, etc. It is a well-settled principle of law that these rights cannot be curtailed without resorting to the due process of law. (Kass, 2007) The grievous violation of the right to life and human dignity has been witnessed in recent Israel Palestine. The grievous violation of the right to life and human dignity has been witnessed in recent Israel-Palestine. After the outbreak of war on 7 October 2023, Israeli authorities initiated a series of bombardments and airstrikes across various parts of the Gaza Strip, resulting in civilian casualties, displacement of masses, and destruction of houses and other infrastructure. Ground incursions and heavy fighting were also witnessed in several parts of occupied territory, namely Beit Hanoun, south of Gaza City, eastern Deir al Balah, northeastern Khan Younis, as well as in eastern, central, and western Rafah. These attacks from the ground and airstrikes from the air, and sea have ended the lives of thousands of people and resulted in the denial of the fundamental right to life. According to the Ministry of Health in Gaza, between 7 October 2023 and 14 June 2024, at least 37,266 Palestinians were killed and 85,102 were injured in Gaza. (The Question of Palestine , 2024) The right to life has sanctity in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR). The Geneva Convention Relative to the Protection of Civilian Persons in Time of War is dedicated to protecting the civilian population in armed conflict. Article 27 of the convention protects civilians against acts of violence and threat. (Shaw, 2008). These attacks and failure to respect the principle of international humanitarian law resulted in the denial of the fundamental right to life.

2) Threat to Children's Lives and Women's Rights

I- The Children and women are among those who suffered most in the armed conflict. The conditions of women's and children's rights require immediate response. Since the outbreak of war on 7 October, thousands of Palestinian people have lost their lives as a result of Israel's attack on occupied territory. The Health Ministry in Gaza reports that Israel has ended the lives of 40000 individuals, with women and children accounting for 70% of this total. (Reuters, 2024) The women are deprived of their fundamental rights of dignity, sanitation, right to health, etc. The women and children are in the middle of this worst

human catastrophe. The mass destruction of houses forced the women to live in temporary shelter tents where they were not able to maintain menstrual hygiene with dignity. The pregnant woman and newborn are not getting basic human necessities, which results in miscarriage, and if the child is born, he is at great risk of malnutrition. OHCHR estimated that 155,000 pregnant women and 20,000 children are at a life-threatening risk. Articles 14 and 18 of the Fourth Geneva Convention mandate all the parties for the safety, security, and well-being of the children and expected women.

3) Violation of the Right to Freedom of Speech and Expression

Violation of right to freedom of speech and expression has been violated constantly by the authorities in occupied Palestine and Israel. The authorities are using various means like torture, harassment, false prosecution, and assault to lower the voices of people committed to the cause of society. Report issued by the UN Independent International Commission of Inquiry on the Occupied Palestinian Territory, including East Jerusalem, and Israel has disclosed the fact that the Israeli authorities are limiting this right by labeling the members of civil society as terrorists. The Israeli authorities also restricted the funding to the civil society groups to put pressure on these groups and to silence the dissenting opinion of the human defenders and civil society activists. (The rights of civil society members are being violated by all entities in Israel and the Occupied Palestinian Territory, UN Commission of Inquiry says; Israeli Government restrictions intrinsically linked to occupation, 2023)

Israel has imposed internet shutdowns in Gaza on various occasions to prevent journalists from reporting the anti-human catastrophe. The electricity cut off by the Israeli authorities resulted in the loss of connection of media houses with its aid workers and reporters. All was done to restrict the world from exploring the deteriorating human conditions. This conflict may be regarded as the deadliest period for the reporters who cover the devastating conditions of the Palestinians. Various Palestinian journalists have suffered a lot in the form of arrests, and killings of family members while fulfilling their professional commitments.

The right to freedom of speech and expression is a natural right which has an important place in the international human rights law

and humanitarian law. International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights tends to protect the freedom of speech and expression. (International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, 1966).

4. Disproportionate Use of Force and Indiscriminate Attacks

IHL requires that the harm caused to civilians or civilian property must not be excessive in relations to the anticipated military advantage gained from an attack. Reports indicated that Israeli airstrikes resulted in significant civilian casualties, including women and children. The sheer scale of civilian harm, compared to the military objectives, raised concerns about whether the attacks were proportionate. IHL mandates that all parties in a conflict distinguish between military targets and civilians, with attacks only being permissible against the former. Gaza is one of the most densely populated areas in the world, making it difficult to conduct military operations without affecting civilians. Allegations surfaced that Israel's airstrikes did not sufficiently distinguish between military targets and civilian areas, leading to significant collateral damage.

Oxfam and Human Rights Watch have documented that the Israeli authorities have imposed collective punishment on the territory following the Hamas-led 7 October attacks in Israel. The Israeli authority symbolised tactics of starvation, destruction of hospitals, and cutting down on electricity and water supply as a weapon of war to achieve their ends. It constitutes a grave violation of the Fourth Geneva Convention and customary international humanitarian law that restricts the imposition of collective punishments. The vast majority of Gaza's population has also been subjected to forced eviction as a consequence of collective punishments. (Human Rights Watch, 2024).

5) Targeting of Civilian Infrastructure

Physical destruction in Gaza has been massive: 60% of the territory's total housing stock (234,000 homes) is damaged, 46,000 of which are destroyed (Rogers, 2023). Civilian structures such as homes, schools, hospitals, and religious sites are protected under IHL unless they are being used for military purposes. Destruction of Infrastructure: Israeli forces were accused of targeting and destroying civilian infrastructure, including residential buildings, schools, hospitals, and places of worship. In many cases, there was little to no evidence that these structures were being used for military purposes, making such

attacks potentially unlawful under IHL. It clearly violates Article 18 of the Fourth Geneva Convention, which protects the hospital or protected from being attacked in any circumstance.

6) Failure to Provide Adequate Warnings

IHL mandates that parties to a conflict shall take adequate precautions to avoid or minimise damage to civilians. This includes providing warnings to civilians when possible. Although Israel has a policy of issuing warnings (e.g., "roof knocking" or dropping leaflets), there were instances in the 2023 conflict where warnings were either not provided, insufficient in time, or ineffective, leading to civilian casualties. Article 57(2) (c) of Additional Protocol I of 1977 imposes a duty on the parties to give adequate warning before to ensure the interest of the civilian population.

7) Siege and Blockade of Gaza

"We are imposing a complete siege on [Gaza]. Everything is closed without electricity, food, water, or fuel. We are fighting human animals, and we act accordingly" This is the statement given, On 9 October 2023, by Israel's Minister of Defense. On the very same evening, Israeli authorities cut off all water supplies. On the day of the Hamas-led attacks on Israel, 7 October, Israel cut the electricity that it supplies to Gaza, which is the main source of electricity in the occupied territory. Due to the suspension of electricity, water and wastewater facilities in Gaza, survival in Palestine becomes impossible. According to the Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs, as of 16 February, water production in Gaza stood at just 5.7% of what it was before the current hostilities. The lack of potable water, as well as the damage and destruction of sewage and wastewater infrastructure, has led to the outbreak of diseases, including Hepatitis A and diarrhea, as well as cases of severe dehydration. The lack of water for cleaning, the breakdown of sanitation infrastructure, and the resulting contamination of the environment have also been a major cause of disease outbreaks. International humanitarian law mandates the occupying power that is Israel to ensure the basic necessities of the civilians in occupied territory. This is a positive obligation of IHL that mandates Israel to protect Palestinians' right to water and to take every deliberate, concrete action to ensure the full realisation of these rights. Depriving a population of access to water amounts to collective punishment of the civilian population, a war crime. The water right, which includes the right to safe

and clean drinking water and sanitation, is also a human right derived from the right to life andn adequate standard of living (Human Rights Watch, 2024).

The blockade of Gaza, enforced by Israel, severely limits the movement of goods and people, leading to a humanitarian crisis. While the blockade itself predates 2023, its intensification during the conflict raised further concerns. The blockade and military actions disrupted essential services, including access to water, electricity, and medical care, exacerbating the humanitarian situation in violation of IHL, which requires ensuring the civilian population's access to necessities.

8) Use of Explosive Weapons in Populated Areas

II- Human Rights Watch and Oxfam believe that Israeli forces' use of explosive weapons with wide-area effects in populated areas of Gaza raises significant concerns over Israel's compliance with the international humanitarian law principles of distinction and proportionality. Various reports published in December certified that most of the bombs dropped by Israel on the occupied territory were unguided bombs. Washington Post has confirmed that Israeli forces dropped over 22,000 US-origin munitions on Gaza during the first 45 days of the hostilities. (Human Rights Watch, 2024). The use of heavy explosive weapons in densely populated areas, such as Gaza, can have indiscriminate effects, making it difficult to limit damage to military targets. Human Rights Watch has confirmed that Israel has used white phosphorus in Gaza, which put the lives of civilians at stake. White phosphorous is a very dangerous substance that does a chemical reaction when it comes in connection with oxygen and creates a lot of heat and burns the body till the exhaustion of oxygen. Reports from the 2023 conflict highlighted the use of such weapons, which resulted in widespread destruction and significant civilian harm, calling into question the legality of such tactics under IHL

9) Obstruction of Humanitarian Assistance

III- After the attack of Hamas on Israel, The Israel Authorities have stringent security on the borders connecting Palestine with other countries to restrict humanitarian aid. On 9 October, they restricted the entry of the vehicles carrying aid for the victims. For the next 12 days, Israel closed all of Gaza's access points and continued the bombing of the Rafah border crossing with Egypt. On 21 October, Israeli authorities

grant permission only to 20 trucks carrying humanitarian aid to enter Gaza through the Rafah Crossing. In contrast, before the outbreak of hostilities, the population of Gaza was getting an average of 500 truckloads of food, water, medicine, and other essential items every single day. Since November, people in northern Gaza have not been able to access drinking water. This lack of water resulted in illness and diseases. After the substantive reduction of essential commodities, the people of Palestine caught diseases like diarrhea and Hepatitis A, as well as dehydration. Oxfam has reported that only 2% of the total food supply was reached between 8 October and 25 October compared to the food supply reached before 8 October. This arbitrary exercise of power by the Occupying authority violated IHL because Article 33 of the Fourth Geneva Convention prohibits the imposition of collective punishment. (Human Rights Watch, 2024).

5. Conclusion

The continuous struggle between Israel and Hamas in Gaza, particularly since 7 October, 2023, has raised significant charges and concerns about violations of international humanitarian law (IHL). International humanitarian law, particularly the Geneva Conventions, establishes norms for protecting civilians and ensuring humane treatment during hostilities. The situation in Gaza since 7 October, 2023, reflects a complex and terrible struggle with substantial concerns about violations of international humanitarian law. While Israel has the right to defend itself against attacks, IHL requires that its military operations follow the principles of distinction, proportionality, and precaution. The international community has urged for thorough investigations into suspected Israeli violations, underlining the importance of accountability and the preservation of civilian life under international humanitarian law.

6. Recommendations

The international community can use a variety of strategies to confront and stop Israel's violations of international humanitarian law (IHL) against the Palestinian people in the Gaza Strip. These tactics can range from diplomatic pressure to legal action and humanitarian assistance. Here are some key recommendations and suggestions:

- i. **Diplomatic Pressure and Condemnation:** The UN Security Council and General Assembly can issue resolutions denouncing violations of international humanitarian law and calling for an immediate cease of hostilities. Although not always enforceable, such resolutions put further pressure on Israel. Countries can downgrade diplomatic relations with Israel, recall ambassadors, or apply diplomatic sanctions in response to its acts.
- ii. **Economic and Trade Sanctions:** Imposing targeted sanctions against Israeli officials, military commanders, and entities directly involved in IHL violations. These may include travel bans, asset freezes, and financial transaction restrictions. Some nations may apply trade restrictions or embargoes on military-related goods and services, which could influence Israel's defense industry.
- iii. **International Legal Action:** Support the ICC's investigations and prosecutions of alleged war crimes and violations of international humanitarian law in Gaza. The international community can exert pressure to cooperate with ICC investigations and promote accountability. Countries having universal jurisdiction legislation can prosecute persons who commit war crimes under IHL, even if the crimes occurred outside of their boundaries. Submit complaints and proof of IHL violations to international human rights organisations, such as the UN Human Rights Council, which can conduct investigations and produce findings on infractions.
- iv. **Humanitarian Interventions and Assistance:** Increase humanitarian assistance to Gaza through international organisations such as the United Nations, Red Cross, and non-governmental organisations (NGOs), ensuring that help reaches civilians despite the fighting. Press Israel to allow the creation of humanitarian corridors and safe zones in Gaza, ensuring that civilians have access to basic services and can safely exit war zones. Deploy international observers or peacekeepers to monitor the situation on the ground, document transgressions, and provide independent reports to the global community.
- v. **Public Advocacy and Mobilisation:** Raise global public awareness about IHL violations in Gaza through campaigns, protests, and social media, increasing government pressure to act. Increase the ability of non-governmental organisations (NGOs) and civil society organisations

that seek to document and expose violations of international humanitarian law, fight for victims' rights, and support legal action.

- vi. **Engagement with Regional Powers:** Engage regional powers and organisations, such as the Arab League or the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC), to mediate and advocate for an end to hostilities and adherence to IHL. Use diplomatic leverage over Israel's regional partners to persuade them to compel Israel to follow international humanitarian law.
- vii. **Conditional Aid and Military Assistance:** Countries that provide military support to Israel may condition this aid on Israel's commitment to IHL, which requires rigorous adherence to international norms in military operations. In circumstances of egregious transgressions, countries may withhold military or economic help to Israel until it makes concrete steps to comply with IHL.
- viii. **Promoting Peace Negotiations:** The international community can encourage Israeli and Palestinian representatives to resume peace talks to establish a long-term settlement that respects both parties' rights and dignity. Provide mediation and arbitration services to resolve conflicts following IHL principles and achieve a long-term and equitable peace agreement.

By combining these tactics, the international community can put enormous pressure on Israel to follow international humanitarian law, decrease civilian suffering, and contribute to long-term peace and stability in the region.

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